

KICMA Reach

A Peer Reviewed Journal of Commerce & Management

Vol. 7 • No. 2 • July-December 2021

KICMA-B. School

Kerala Institute of Co-operative Management (KICMA)
Neyyadam, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala
Website: www.kicma.ac.in

Advertising and Social Media Management and their Interrelationship in Video Monetization

Dr. Sreedhar P. Nair¹ & Mrs. Shaly Marshal²

ABSTRACT

Social media and advertising are those terms which are commonly in use and have become the largest and most meaningful pieces of digital marketing. Video monetization is the new term which are introduced in the past few years. Monetization of the videos means getting paid for publishing creative videos on social media sites with the support of advertising. Advertisers can gather more information about their potential customers from social media sites. As social media continues to evolve, successful brands will adapt their strategies to accommodate an ever changing audience. Keeping track of the latest technological and social trends the video creators and advertising firms can enjoy the benefit of monetization in future. However, a thorough study of the interrelationship of advertising, social media and video monetization are relevant today.

Key words: Social media, Advertising, Video Monetization, Digital Marketing

INTRODUCTION

Advertising is a marketing tactic involving paying for space to promote a product or services. The goal of advertising is to reach people most likely to be willing to pay for a company's products or services and induce them to buy. From the point of view of advertisers, it is relevant to know where their target audiences lie. It is also important for the advertisers that in which network their target falls. Social media are one of the important communication tools to find out the targeted audience for advertisers. They need people who can design comprehensive social media strategy to increase visibility, membership and traffic across the web. Most social networking companies eventually monetize the creative videos through advertising. Video monetization means getting paid for the videos you create. People watch, like or subscribe and you get paid a sum of money for it. If we are creating videos regarding lifestyle, food, fashion, personalities and luxury brands we should focus on the social media such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram etc. The term video monetization introduced to the public from the year 2018.

Millions of people and entrepreneurs making and uploading video contents to the web regularly. The key to succeeding in video monetization is to create and upload valuable and quality material that the viewers want to see. Advertisements are the major source of revenue from these videos. The interrelationship of social media, advertising and video monetization will bring fruitful results in the near future.

¹ Head of the Department of Commerce, St. Michael's College, Cherthala

² M.Phil Scholar, Research & PG Department of Commerce, SB College, Changanassery

<u>Year</u>	<u>Major Milestones</u>
1472	: The first print ad was published for a book
1704	:The first newspaper ad was published in US
1835	:The first poster ads were introduced
1890	: Mailing post cards
1922	: Ads through Radio
1941-1950	: Ads through TV& Telephone
1960-1990	: Golden Age of advertising. Companies started to introduce characters, brands& packaging for their Products
1992	: Internet usage started
1994	: Display advertising started with the first Banner Ads from AT&T.
2000	: The first Mobile Advertising started via SMS.
2007	: Mobile advertising came to Smart Phones APPLE releases the first iPhone.

ADVERTISING- Evolution

2008	: The launch of the App Store. Facebook launches Social ads YouTube launches Video Overlays
2010	: Social media get enlarged
2011	: Native Advertising starts
2014 onwards	: Advertising grows in to its new dimensions

SOCIAL MEDIA – Evolution

<u>Years</u>	<u>Events</u>
1980-1990	: Infancy stage of social media BBS- First public movement to make the internet social
1997	: AOL- American Online, an ancestor of social network
2003	: The first social media site Six Degrees was introduced by Andrew Weinreich : MySpace , First modern social network founded by Tom Anderson and hrisDe Wolfe.
2004	: The “Facebook.com” founded by Mark Zuckerberg
2005	: YouTube introduced
2006	: Facebook opened to public Twitter began as “Micro blogging” service.
2010	: Instagram created by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger.

2011	: Snapchat founded. Facebook bought Instagram.
2012	: Facebook holds its IPO (Initial Public Offering).
2015	: Facebook market value is nearly \$245 billion.
2018	: Social media became an integral part of the world.

VIDEO MONETIZATION – Evolution

<u>Years</u>	<u>Major Milestones</u>
2006	: First advertising concepts launched
2007	: In video ads launched
2008	: Promoted videos launched : Pre-roll ads launched
2009	: Individual video partnerships launched : Skippable pre-roll ads launched
2010	: YouTube Mobile ads launched
2018 on wards	: YouTube introduced new parameter of monetizing videos by PrioritizingWatch time : Social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter etc, are promoted video monetization

REQUIREMENTS TO VIDEO MONETIZATION

Here the focus is given to how the videos are monetized in social media such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter by using advertising.

YouTube Monetization- steps.

1. Qualifications for the monetization process
 - Create own Channel
 - Join in YouTube Partner Program.
 - Upload videos should be free from copy right claim.
 - Attain 1000 Subscribers
 - Should have 4000 hours watch time within one year.
2. Link with AdSense account.
3. Apply for monetization and activate the AdSense account.
 - Select the types of ads which are needed in our videos.
4. Give personal details and bank account details

Facebook Monetization- steps.

1. Create a Facebook page in our Facebook account.
2. Minimum 10000 Likes or Followers.
3. Average 1 minute views for 3 minute videos.
4. There should be 30000 one minute views or watch time within 60 days.
5. The Facebook page must have minimum 90 days life.

Instagram Monetization- steps.

1. Buy and sell genuine accounts.
2. Grow and sell accounts.
3. Instagram influencer.
4. Drop shipping.
5. Social media management.

Twitter Monetization- steps.

1. To enable monetization,
 - Duration of the video should have two minutes.
2. In-stream video ads.
 - Pre- roll ads.
 - Mid- roll ads.
 - Post- roll ads.
3. Sponsorships.

Types of Advertisement used for Monetization.

1. Display ads – method of advertisements used in websites social media platforms or other digital mediums.
2. Overlay ads – Image ads that appear overlaid on the bottom of the videos.
3. Sponsored ads – These are the paid posts or promoted posts that contain link to the homepage of the specific product's website of the sponsor for which the blogger receives compensation in the form of money, products or services.
4. Skippable video ads - These ads can be skip after 5 seconds.
5. Non skippable video ads – These can only exit by the user after watching the full video ad generally having 15 - 30 seconds duration.

RELEVANCE OF ADVERTISING AND SOCIAL MEDIA IN VIDEO MONETIZATION

Advertisement has a key role in our social lives. Traditionally ads is a paid form of exposure or promotion by some sponsor that reaches through various traditional media such as television, newspaper, commercial radio advertisements, magazine mail, etc. But now in modern era its form and presentation has changed a lot. It has influenced the mass audience of a huge world to change traditional to modern hand held devices like smart phones, tablets, laptops, etc.

Changing video viewing habits provide new opportunities for video content publishers or video creators and advertisement firms. Here arises the revolutionary role of social media. Social media are interactive computer mediated technology that facilitates the creation and sharing of informative ideas, career interests and other forms of expressions via virtual communities and networks. Social media advertising is the planning and execution of advertising campaigns through the channels. |The reason is that by using advertisements through social media the firms can reach the brands to the user's finger tips. The fact is that clients are hanging out in the online social communities such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram etc.

Now a days the video marketing strategy has changed and its next level named "video monetization" has emerged. Monetization literally means to earn money. Video monetization is the process, which involves getting paid for publishing our videos on online platforms by using methods like inserting ads offering subscriptions, getting sponsorships, doing reviews etc.

Advertisements are one of the best ways to make revenue and profit from the social media accounts. Informative and creative videos represent a source of profit for so many brands and companies. Video monetization process can be done through the medium of various social networking sites such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter etc. Monetization of a video is always supported by social media and advertising, so these are interrelated to each other.

POSITIVE IMPACTS

1. Content violations are strictly prohibited.
2. Quality of the content is necessary.
3. Our own creativities are motivated.
4. Debated social issues are strictly prohibited for monetization.
5. Content of the video should be original, including music, graphics, images etc.

NEGATIVE IMPACTS

1. Non- skippable video ads may reduce the viewership of our videos.
2. Branded contents are not monetized.

3. Time consuming for technical supports.
4. Linking of AdSense accounts with other business accounts may create issues in monetization.

CONCLUSION

The key factor of social media in monetization has been the immense amount of personal information available to advertisers. From this information the advertisers can understand the likes and dislikes of the users. The ability to access and analyze the data from social media are important for the success of monetization. The studies shows that the user spends an average of 2 or more hours in social media accounts everyday for messaging, video creations, video sharing etc. Approximately 2 million business houses use social media advertising for promotions. So this paper can be concluded with the assumption that the modern advertising methods are more appropriate, dependent and fruitful towards social media in video monetization process. In future the video monetization will become one of the top revenue generation techniques for our modern society and its advantage will be tasted by upcoming companies, ad firms, users of the social media and the owners of the networking sites.

REFERENCES

- EnteSamrambham (2019), *Business magazine*, vol.3, Issue 24, February 2019, pp. 26-29.
- Dhanam (2018), *Business magazine*, June 2018, pp.24.
- <http://rocketium.com>
- <http://www.businessnewsdaily.com>
- <http://www.brid.tv>
- <http://www.wonderopolis.org>
- <http://www.slideshare.net>
- <http://sites.google.com>